

Study of the Complexes obtained from Interaction between Copper(II) Chelates of 2-Hydroxyaromatic Ketones and Aralkyl Monoamines

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Manuscript received 10 October 1984, revised 14 April 1986, accepted 23 April 1986

The title interaction has been studied in ethanol medium under reflux conditions and also in restricted amount of the solvent at room temperature. Square-planar Schiff base complexes result under the first set of conditions. But at room temperature diamine adducts seem to be formed. A mechanism envisaging an initial rapid coordination of the primary amine to the central metal ion has been proposed for the Schiff base complex formation reaction.

A primary amine is expected to interact with transition metal chelate in at least two distinct ways. Either it may coordinate with the central metal ion to form a new compound with expanded coordination number or it may react with the coordinated ligand first, with subsequent possibilities of the formation of Schiff base complexes. Though convincing evidence for the former type of interaction is lacking, Nunez and Eichhorn¹ postulated the formation of adducts as intermediates in such reactions. However, the latter course of reaction has been suggested by some workers²⁻⁵ for metal chelates with hydroxyaromatic carbonyl compounds.

Adduct formation should be possible in cases where stereochemical and energetic factors favour a slow condensation reaction. Using copper(II) chelates 2-hydroxyaromatic ketones, interaction with alkyl monoamines has been investigated in order to confirm or discard the possibilities of adduct formation as postulated by Nunez¹ and Janecks⁶.

Experimental

All chemicals were of reagent grade quality. The 2-hydroxyaromatic ketones were prepared by Frus

- 1; X = H, R = CH₃
- 2; X = 5-CH₃, R = CH₃
- 3; X = 5-Cl, R = CH₃
- 4; X = 5-Cl, R = C₆H₅

reaction from appropriate phenolic esters. Copper(II) chelates (1-4) were prepared by the reported methods^{7,8}.

The Schiff base complexes were first obtained in ethanolic medium by condensing each of the above copper(II) chelates separately with benzyl and β -phenylethyl amines as detailed below:

Interaction of chelates with the primary amines under reflux conditions: Copper(II) chelates of the carbonyl compound (0.01 mol) was suspended in ethanol (~50 ml) and the amine (0.02 mol) incorporated into the mixture. The mixture was refluxed for 15 min and cooled. Reddish-brown complexes separated were purified by recrystallisation from benzene-ethanol (1:1) mixture. Compounds so prepared (Cu-1 to Cu-8) have been listed in Table 1 along with their analytical and magnetic data. Identical compounds could also be obtained by reacting copper(II) acetate with requisite quantity of the Schiff base in presence of an external base.

Interaction of Cu²⁺ chelates at 20° with primary amines in presence of excess ethanol: Freshly prepared and dried Cu²⁺ chelates (0.01 mol) was taken with about four times the volume of ethanol. The mixture was thoroughly ground in a mortar for 5 min. Appropriate amine (0.02 mol) was then allowed to drop into the mixture in a mortar with constant trituration and the contents were quickly transferred to a sintered glass crucible and filtered under efficient suction. The solid in the crucible was again moistured with methanol/ethanol (2 ml) and stirred thoroughly. The solvent

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF COPPER(II) COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	Reactants		Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} ^a B.M.
	Chelate	Amine		N	Cu	
Cu-1	1	Benzyl	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cu	5.20 (5.47)	12.08 (12.41)	1.60
Cu-2	1	β -Phenylethyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cu	5.26 (5.19)	11.42 (11.47)	1.59
Cu-3	2	Benzyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ H ₂ O ₂ Cu	5.50 (5.19)	11.36 (11.37)	1.59
Cu-4	2	β -Phenylethyl	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ Cu	5.21 (4.93)	10.75 (11.19)	1.59
Cu-5	3	Benzyl	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ Co ₂ ⁺ Cu	5.04 (4.82)	10.80 (10.94)	1.59
Cu-6	3	β -Phenylethyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ Cu	5.00 (4.60)	10.18 (10.43)	1.64
Cu-7	4	Benzyl	C ₄₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ Cu	3.39 (3.97)	9.25 (9.01)	1.54
Cu-8	4	β -Phenylethyl	C ₄₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ Cu	4.14 (3.82)	8.80 (8.67)	1.58

^aAt 239 k.

was then removed by suction. It was repeated 2-3 times. Products were dried finally in a vacuum desiccator.

Characterisation of the complexes prepared by the above methods was done by micro-analysis of the elements and estimation of copper as cupric oxide after igniting the complex to a constant weight.

Infrared spectra were taken with a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer using KBr pallets. A Beckman 25 uv-vis spectrometer was used for electronic spectra measurements. Electrolytic conductance was measured in chloroform as solvent at room temperature. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by Gouy's method

Results and Discussion

The compounds were found to be non-electrolytes.

Infrared frequencies characteristic of these complexes are listed in Table 2. The broad band envelope in 2 800-200 cm⁻¹ region, present in cases of free Schiff bases due to intra-molecular H-bonded phenolic group⁹, was absent in the prepared compounds. Deprotonation and simultaneous formation of Cu—O bond can thus be inferred. The ν_{O-N} mode absorbed at marginally

TABLE 2—PRINCIPAL IR BANDS (CM⁻¹) OF COPPER(II) COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	ν_{C-N}	ν_{O-O}	δ_{OH_2}	δ_{OH_2}	ν_{O-O}	ν_{Cu-N}	ν_{Cu-O}
Cu-1	1 590	1 570, 1 525	1 435	1 360	1 320	415	312
Cu-3	1 610	1 580, 1 530	1 447	1 345	1 325	370	340
Cu-4	1 610	1 590, 1 530	1 460	1 340	1 315	360	337
Cu-5	1 597	1 585, 1 520	1 450	1 345	1 318	360	335
Cu-6	1 592	1 555, 1 515	1 445	1 363	1 315	365	340
Cu-7	1 590	1 555, 1 505	1 440	-	1 317	360	327
Cu-8	1 595	1 575, 1 520	1 450	-	1 325	355	335

lower frequencies¹⁰ (1 610-1 590 cm⁻¹) as compared to those of the free Schiff bases (1 620-1 600 cm⁻¹). This indicates involvement of azomethine nitrogen in bonding¹¹.

New bonds in the 415-355 and 390-315 cm⁻¹ regions were assigned respectively to Cu ← N and Cu—O stretching modes¹². Presence of several bands in 520-450 cm⁻¹ region and slight increase in intensity and frequency shift were observed. These are probably due to the out-of-plane ring deformations. Metal ligand stretching mode due to vibrational coupling also is likely to give some of these absorptions.

Uv-vis absorption spectra (Table 3) was strikingly similar for all the eight compounds showing bands in 630-615, 380-360 and 308-304 nm regions. The lowest energy band

TABLE 3—UV-VISIBLE SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	λ_{max} ^a (nm)		
	1	2	3
Cu-1	615 (215)	360 (9 210)	308 (11 760)
Cu-2	620 (204)	360 (8 600)	308 (12 950)
Cu-3	620 (216)	370 (10 790)	305 (12 950)
Cu-4	625 (216)	370 (11 350)	305 (14 750)
Cu-5	630 (209)	370 (12 770)	350 (14 165)
Cu-6	625 (310)	370 (14 190)	303 (14 460)
Cu-7	625 (225)	380 (12 120)	305 (12 260)
Cu-8	625 (175)	380 (11 425)	303 (12 600)

^aFigures in parentheses represent molar extinction coefficients.

The band in the visible region appeared as a broad shoulder preceding the intense band around 370 nm.

in the visible region was due to the merger of the

²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g}, ²B_{1g} → ²B_{2g} and ²B_{1g} → ²E_g

transitions in a D_{4h} symmetry^{14,15}. The strong absorption at 350-360 nm is expected to be due to ligand-copper(II) charge transfer¹⁷. The highest

energy band appearing at almost a constant wave length (~ 305 nm) is caused by $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transitions of the amine aromatic rings^{18,19}.

The μ_{eff} values (Table 1) of 1.54-1.64 B.M. for these compounds were appreciably lower than the spin-only value of 1.73 for a d^9 system. This may be due to the quenching of the unpaired spin in the metal ion as unpaired spins on the adjacent Cu^{II} ions coupled by super exchange type of interaction involving a π -electronic pathway across the bridging oxygen atoms²² arising from partial dimerisation of the Cu^{II} complexes in solid state.

Reaction carried out at room temperature gave solids of colours varying from bright green to olive green. However, the correct stoichiometry could be determined only for compounds obtained by the intraction of benzylamine and chelates 1, 2 and 3 ($\text{Cu-9} : \text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cu}$, $\text{Cu-10} : \text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cu}$, and $\text{Cu-11} : \text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2\text{Cu}$). Their characterisation by infrared spectral data suggest them to be adducts of amines with the metal-ketone complexes. Their complexes gave a doublet of medium intensity having a maxima in 3 310 to 3 250 cm^{-1} region (which is ~ 50 cm^{-1} lower than those for pure amines^{23,24}). Additional new bands at 1 590-1 560 and 1 212-1 190 cm^{-1} regions were also obtained due to δ_{NH} and ν_{ON} vibration modes^{25,26}. The broad intense band at $1\ 625 \pm 5$ cm^{-1} was due to ν_{CO} mode²⁷. The magnetic moment values of these compounds are found to be in the range 1.84-1.90 B.M.

These adducts are relatively unstable and decompose even during preparation, as observed in adducts of β -phenylethyl amine with metal-ketone complexes. However, the adducts changed into tetracoordinated Schiff base complexes on refluxing in ethanolic solutions. The reaction can thus be envisaged as the initial bonding of amine to the metal in the chelate to give adduct as intermediate which facilitates the nucleophilic attack on the carbonyl group resulting in the removal of a molecule of water.

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